

THE ISSUE OF ENTERING ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *The given article presents the secrets of entering into entrepreneurship, which are necessary for entrepreneurs who have taken a step into entrepreneurship in order to fully form an enterprise and achieve the desired economic goal. It also gives direction to the prospects for new business activity.*

Keywords: *entrepreneurship, enterprise, idea, start-up capital, plan, market, marketing, strategy.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that the new stage of entrepreneurship in our country at the present time is a new stage of entrepreneurship in the independent Republic of Uzbekistan, taking the example of the advanced countries of the world, developing with enthusiasm and being civilized. Therefore: "In the development strategy of new Uzbekistan, the creation of the necessary conditions for entrepreneurship is defined as a priority task" [1.147]. Because the expansion of the ranks of entrepreneurs and the rapid development of their activities is the driver of the reforms carried out in our country, the development of our society and strong support for our prosperous life, the most important guarantee of the stable growth of our economy. Therefore, the increasingly improving business environment in our country is a clear confirmation of this.

Therefore, in order to achieve the desired economic development, it would be advisable for each new entrepreneur who has started entrepreneurial activity in our country to carefully study the secrets and true nature of entrepreneurship. It helps a modern entrepreneur to arm himself with the necessary theoretical and practical skills, which are the basis not only for his own, but also for social development.

Analysis of literature on the topic. It is worth mentioning that the historic decision of the head of state "On measures to simplify the regulation of entrepreneurial activity by the state" defined the New Development Strategy of our country and implemented the principles of a market economy, that is, to give freedom to entrepreneurs, to expand their ranks in every possible way and develop their activities, it is proposed to cover this topic and substantiate it theoretically [2].

In foreign scientific and popular literature, one can find different, comprehensive approaches to the topic:

- Kazuma Tateishi (The Eternal Dux of Entrepreneurship, M. 1990) expressed entrepreneurship as a holistic, serious, permanent economic way of life [4];

- Paul Hawken (The Secret of Success - Minsk, 1995) spoke about the secrets of entrepreneurship [5];

- Eric Ries (The Business Started from Scratch. Lean Startup Style. - T. 2021) described his experience in business, that is, the main mistakes made and achievements [6];

- Annenkov P. (Million Dollar Mistakes – T. 2022) mentioned typical mistakes that can be made in business [7];

- Philip Kotler (Marketing from A to Z. - T. 2021) can be called the father of marketing science, that is, he was the first to describe marketing as a lever of entrepreneurial activity [7].

Besides that, in the series of textbooks, Mario Bruhlmann, The Ten Commandments for Entrepreneurs. - T. 2021[9]; Duncan Clark. Alibaba. The Place That Jack Ma Built. - T. 2022 [10] and others [11] also covered all the intricacies of entering entrepreneurship.

Therefore, while comparing, it turned out that the secrets of entering entrepreneurship at the level of the above-mentioned foreign authors have recently been little studied by scientists in our country. Therefore, the main attention in the article was focused on highlighting the main features of the activity that they encounter when entering into entrepreneurship.

Research methodology. In the given article, it was considered the issue of the formation of entrepreneurship from the point of view of historical, economic, logical principles, a deterministic approach and the method of discourse analysis. Also, the methods of scientific abstraction and system analysis were used in the research.

Research results. It is known that the basis of the economy of any country is the household, enterprises and organizations. This is a whole system of production relations. Households, the state are consumers of various goods and services, and enterprises-organizations act as their producers. That is why their role is very high in the modern world economy; this growth leads to globalization.

Therefore, an organization is an association of a group of people, some kind of organizational structure, working together to achieve specific goals and constantly interacting with the external environment, using material and human resources. By the will of life, the starting point of any organization is an initiatory person or group armed with some idea, which is its source. Their ideological fundamental desires are to achieve a clearly defined goal, starting from simple activities, and then to develop the enterprise to a level of complex development. This process begins with a simple desire, then turns into a clear, firm fundamental goal and strives for specific activities. We are talking about starting a business.

So, the goal of a future entrepreneur in organizing an enterprise is to receive income (profit) from it for many years. This follows from the wisdom of this entrepreneur, that is, from his philosophical views. He knows that:

“At present, in the process of creating a socially oriented "Uzbek model" of market economy in New Uzbekistan, entrepreneurship is a leading force in ensuring the intended economic development”[12].

Therefore, every founder who starts a new business constantly strives to make a profit, but not everyone knows how to do this. They should not ignore: “Therefore, in order to improve the business environment in our country from year to year, they are given ample opportunities and many reforms are being implemented to support them. Of course, an effective mechanism for this has been developed and is constantly being improved. Adequate legal and regulatory documents have been developed and put into practice by the government for these measures” [12].

Of course, new entrepreneurs should have a full understanding of this, and it is important for them to know how to use such opportunities.

Moreover, an enterprising person or group armed with a new idea differs from others in that they have a full understanding of how to make a profit. "Ideas are a cheap product. Implementation is more valuable than an idea" [7,5]. More precisely, thanks to their long research, they know which sector, industry, type of activity or geographic region they are currently inclined

to attract investment. By the way, in which country do you want to start a business? This is also important. All this means that "the philosophy of entrepreneurship is the philosophy of practice"ю

However, any ambitious entrepreneur strives not only to achieve the average rate of profit in a competitive market, but also to make a large profit. Therefore, such a motive encourages the entrepreneur to achieve superiority in any competition.

Certainly, this does not happen by itself. This aspiration, the intended goal requires knowledge, experience and high skills from the entrepreneur, and this situation generates the entrepreneur's internal experiences, plans and goals that he pursues with the necessary perfect calculation. All this ultimately forms the entrepreneur's plans for the future, that is, his strategy in this direction.

It is known that to achieve a long-term goal, initial capital is needed, the size of which depends on the chosen industry and scale of production. For example, it is not so difficult to organize a store, a shop or a *paynet*, but to organize an entire major textile factory, a commercial bank, an investment company is a serious matter. We would like to say that the organizational and legal form of the enterprise being created depends on how much money an individual entrepreneur or an initiative group has to achieve the intended goal. If the available funds are sufficient to create the initial capital, it is better to create a limited liability company. If there are insufficient funds or a slight shortage, depending on the situation, closed membership in shares is declared and a limited liability company or a closed joint-stock company is created.

Therefore, when the time comes and a large sum of money is needed for the development of the enterprise, the form of the existing enterprise changes to an open joint-stock company, and the shares of the new enterprise are created by selling. authorized capital and capital on the stock exchange. Thus, the initiators take a place among the founders, create a closed or open joint-stock company, establish the owners of the property, and the enterprise is registered with the State Services Center. For this, such serious issues as the name of the enterprise, form, type of activity, authorized capital, founders and their share, which bank to open an account in, the legal address of the enterprise, a draft of the press, even the Liquidation of the enterprise at some point must be determined in advance, and this information will be recorded in the Charter of the new enterprise.

Besides that, the state duty is paid and a new seal and stamp of the enterprise are ordered. At the same time, it is determined which local tax authority will be contacted, reports will be submitted to it during the activity, taxes and other fees will be paid.

It is also worth noting that when people have free funds, they have the opportunity to choose one of the following ways to use them effectively: placing money in a bank account, in currency, securities or precious metals, buying real estate, investing in business activity. Here, the criterion for assessing a particular opportunity is its income over a certain period of time with little risk. To do this, the initiators must have sufficient financial literacy. Therefore, an entrepreneurial group or an individual entrepreneur must know the type of activity of the future enterprise, the content of contracts, financial and credit transactions, tax burden, the rate of return on invested funds and determine its level in detail, while achieving the expected rate of return with minimal risks and losses for the owners, you must be sure that you can get it. You should also keep in mind situations of insolvency (bankruptcy). Therefore, practice shows that the initiative group is part of the owners of a new enterprise, and when creating an enterprise, a leader appears from their ranks. In this situation, he will be the first manager of the organization, and it may be advisable to choose

a manager - a hired manager. Experience shows that often the same owner-entrepreneur-manager who creates the same enterprise invests in the enterprise.

Thus, while creating any commercial enterprise, it is necessary to clarify the following most important questions: - the type of activity of the enterprise; - the size of the initial capital of the enterprise; - the organizational and legal form of the enterprise; - the expected rate of return on invested capital.

On the contrary, when creating new private enterprises on the basis of old enterprises in the existing state structure, the formality (procedure) will be somewhat different: - there will be no problem determining the type of activity of the enterprise; - their leaders rely on previous management experience; - only if he carries out a complex process that "will not harm anyone", for example, removing the enterprise from state control; - there is practically everything - capacity, means of production, ready workers and even start-up capital.

Therefore, in this situation it is enough to solve the problem of determining the strategy of the reorganized enterprise. But this is not an easy task, this is definitely a difficult situation. Despite this, the fate of a company starting its entrepreneurial activity is completely different, that is, the tasks of managers, starting from "zero", in them represent a slightly different process. The main problem: they have nothing prepared in advance. He has to start everything from scratch, and he does. However, the new entrepreneur should not forget that his main efforts are aimed at the market demand. In such a situation, the proverb of our people comes in handy: "Your father is the market, your mother is the market". The goal is achieved thanks to the market.

In a market economy, there is no other way, and perhaps it is impossible. Of course, the situation is very complicated, and an entrepreneur must understand this. If we remember that the Independent Commonwealth of Nations, like our country, is in the process of transition to a market economy, this question will be somewhat simpler. Because at that time, that is, in the 90s of the last century, the demand for consumer goods among the population was somewhat high, and there was even a deficit. So, we can say that the initial capital spent on creating a new enterprise quickly paid off. Capital costs paid off quickly, and it became easier for microenterprises to grow several times. Of course, this became possible due to the fact that there was almost no competition in the market. Therefore, in contrast to this, today, when a market economy is developing, the situation is completely different. New firms and companies are multiplying like "mushrooms" in the forest. Competition has become much more lively and active. Therefore, a new entrepreneur, a head of an enterprise must understand this situation in all respects. On the contrary, all efforts will be in vain.

Therefore, despite this, it is clear that an entrepreneur who has started a new business will go his own way. In such a situation, the decision of a new entrepreneur is very important. It should also be said that an entrepreneur must always be prepared for unexpected uncertainties, that is, his duty is to feel them, to be able to see them, and he must be able to prepare unexpected situations for competitors. Uncertainty and inconsistency, expected or unexpected continuous changes are an integral part of entrepreneurial risk. Changes in business are normal. Indeed, many decisions made in business are associated with risk and are not without risk. In other words, decisions made without risk cannot be decisions in themselves.

As the famous Japanese businessman Kazuma Tateishi said on this subject: "When it came to making a decision, he followed the "70/30" rule; if 70% believed that the work would be successful, they agreed to start it, and the remaining 30%, skeptical, called for action in case of

failure. He later says that his practice of the "70/30 rule" is somewhat limiting. Sometimes even the "30/70 rule" serves as a better tool" [4.9].

Why does an entrepreneur take risks? What do you want to achieve from this effort, activity, what is the goal? Among the various goals, the most important ones can be listed: production of goods or services, profit, social goals, business development. At the same time, market penetration is a certain problem when it comes to achieving these goals.

In the current period, the trend of the experience of the world economy development shows that in the dynamics of business growth and cost recovery, companies that enter the market with their new goods or services through innovations justify themselves and demonstrate their effectiveness, prospects. The creation of such business enterprises in the current period significantly contributes to the increase in employment and national income in the country and at the same time serves as a "catalyst" for structural changes in the country's economy, or more precisely, the creation of new industries.

Therefore, a new enterprise must be able to withstand and create "immunity" in various market situations. Moreover, it needs to build its "image" in the market. Certainly, we consider it appropriate to say that further activity is not and cannot be risk-free based on risk.

So, let's say an enterprising person has an idea. Now it will be necessary to comprehensively and carefully evaluate, that is, what is the need for this new economic life: technological changes in the current period, changes in demand or changes in public administration, as well as fiscal policy, etc. However, after determining the degree of role of each of these factors, it is possible to estimate how much of the new product or service can be sold in a certain period of time, based on what demand exists today. The volume of production will be adjusted accordingly.

Therefore, at this stage, beginners must realize how correctly they have started working and, conversely, is it worth taking the risk in this attempt? Often, an inexperienced new entrepreneur has a feeling of success. The situation chooses the opposite.

In other words, at the level of the accepted risk, the expected profit in practice will exceed the calculated costs. But here's the thing. This is how they find out whether the abilities of the new entrepreneur are sufficient or insufficient. So, the risk in this attempt must be justified. For this, sufficient knowledge and skills in entrepreneurial activity are necessary. Without them, the beginning of a new activity is unthinkable.

It is known from them that any, even the most advanced, wonderful idea should be brought to life, it is necessary to carefully develop a plan for its rational and safe implementation. However, this is the most difficult component of entrepreneurial activity, and the issue must be approached very seriously. Therefore, the structure and level of the business plan are directly related to the scope of the enterprise being created, that is, the type of activity. Therefore, the same, let's say, comprehensive plan is necessary for every new entrepreneur, as well as a potential investor.

Telling the truth, it is difficult not to dwell on all the details of the business plan, that is, we do not consider it necessary to describe the essence and content of its creation. However, in the process of its creation, we will say that it is necessary to collect complete information about the market, production and financial resources, that is, about the initial capital. This information helps in forecasting and planning. In this regard, it is necessary not to forget about the need for production resources and the optimal group of costs. Also, let's say, a new entrepreneur needs to understand what kind of lack of resources or a number of errors in the organization is in order to

avoid the expected negative result. Therefore, in such a situation, an entrepreneur must deeply understand that he cannot help but fall into the pattern of the current laws of the market economy in his activities. More precisely, he falls under the influence of market relations and acts in this situation as an independent manufacturer of goods.

Therefore, while assessing any project in entrepreneurship from a technical and economic point of view, it is necessary to take into account the market features of the area covering the entrepreneur's activities. At the same time, a new entrepreneur needs to know that the market is divided into local, regional, continental and global markets by geographical features. This means what market it is in, and also indicates what market it plans to export to in the future. However, the market is a constantly changing. That's why, the project, a chronicle of positive changes in demand for goods, an increase in production volumes; a change in the price of resources used and goods sold; planning to reduce production costs as the volume of manufactured products increases; as a result of the introduction of scientific and technological achievements, changes in the technical level of production and its products; we believe that it is necessary to be able to provide financial resources and other necessary information at the time of investment.

Definitely, we will continue, after all organizational work is completed and the production process is established, the demand for this or that resource will increase. At the same time, it is natural that their purchase price will also increase. For example, a change in food prices or an increase in the minimum wage in the country, etc. Of course, this enterprise requires an increase in wages first of all. Another example. Scientific and technical achievements of the competition can cross out the importance of producing a new type of product that has just been put on the production line, on the conveyor. Therefore, when accepting the risk, one can expect unimaginable danger.

Therefore, in our opinion, while developing serious business projects, it would be appropriate to follow the following rules: All long-term projects should be calculated in advance and included in the necessary or at least technical and economic calculations. Therefore, forecasting and assessing the expected situation are associated with a conscious acceptance of risk. The level of risk associated with the start of a particular event varies. It should be noted here that the ability to implement the planned event with minimal risk determines the prospects of your enterprise for any aspiring entrepreneur. In this case, the characteristics of the entrepreneur will be known accordingly. It should also be said that an unexpected situation, that is, an acceptable project of an entrepreneur today, tomorrow may suddenly become ineffective.

However, an entrepreneur should not ignore this. It is clear that various factors unexpectedly affect this. For example, a change in the level of inflation in the economy, various force majeure situations: for example, a pandemic, various natural disasters. Therefore, the real effectiveness of business projects can and will significantly depend on the level of inflation in the country. For doing this, an entrepreneur must determine and track the level of inflation and its changes over certain periods of time. In general, it is impossible to fully understand all the factors, conditions and invisible effects in the process of implementing projects in the complex and comprehensive business activities of the present time. Therefore, we believe that it is advisable to consider other acceptable, backup options, and not just stick to the only way to implement any serious project.

Therefore, the entrepreneur makes the final decision on the implementation of the project. At the same time, he should not only depend on the influencing factors, but also rely on his personal knowledge, experience and especially his feelings.

The next stage of the formation of the enterprise is the attraction of resources and their rational use in the activities of the enterprise. Resources: labor resources; food and material resources; technological resources; financial resources; information technology resources; grouped with transport resources. It is also important that some of them will become the property of the new enterprise. Therefore, at the stage of the formation of the enterprise, the entrepreneur should concentrate their control in his hands as much as possible.

Based on the need to develop the enterprise, the entrepreneur can attract his own funds or additional "foreign" funds. In this case, one can deeply understand that he is evading the authority to manage some part of the enterprise. A frequent occurrence in the life of entrepreneurs is to receive "foreign" funds and stake them on the fate of a new enterprise. If this relationship is an investment or just a loan, their use-investment is not well thought out and appropriate, the consequences will certainly not end well.

In this matter, according to Paul Hawken, one of the most experienced businessmen in the West, it is better not to borrow money. Since nothing is known while starting a new activity, an enterprising entrepreneur, entering into business for the first time, made a warning in this situation. Both the "uncle" who gave the money and the "mare" who received the money lose. As a result, the business will fail. However, a plan is not an action! [5.285]. Amazing!

Surprisingly, many successful enterprises begin with small funds. Depending on the situation, some firms do not want to attract investments in serious cases. On the contrary, world practice shows that many companies attract large initial capital for rapid growth and soon find themselves in a difficult situation: the company goes bankrupt, and investors break it into pieces. Therefore, our advice: an entrepreneur starting a new business should start work at his own expense or, if possible, with a small loan (if possible - preferably). Therefore, it is safe to say that some short-term activity opens the eyes of a new entrepreneur. So, the process of entrepreneurial activity for beginning businessmen goes from simple to complex, and as the future entrepreneur accumulates experience, his interest increases. This is a logical path from a dialectical point of view. On the contrary, the first mistake made on the way to entering entrepreneurship scares many people and even frightens them, and in the end this subject will leave the business altogether. For example, in the practice of the USA, only 30% of newly opened enterprises continue their activities annually, and the rest go bankrupt for various reasons.

However, since the resources were taken and involved in the work, the stage of solving current problems has come. In this regard, it becomes necessary to establish a management structure for the enterprise and there is a need for its rational management. Through the control system created at the enterprise, it is necessary to promptly identify all the shortcomings and subtleties of the activities carried out. Therefore, it will be necessary to eliminate these shortcomings in a timely manner.

In enterprise management, it is important: - to collect the necessary and experienced personnel for this area in a timely manner; - the tasks between them must be clearly defined; - it is also desirable that this personnel be as loyal and knowledgeable as possible.

Along with this, the direct structure of the new enterprise must be developed. If there is production, it will be necessary to establish production technology and additional service areas.

The necessary permits must also be obtained, for example, permission from the nature management structure and, accordingly, the necessary licenses, a certificate for new products. The location, number of workers, employees, specific duties and responsibilities of workers in production must also be determined.

As it was mentioned above, all activities of the new structure are organized, limited to the production of the final product, sales to the target point and making a profit. However, this process continues without stopping, or rather, it repeats itself without stopping. Consequently, this is simple reproduction, and expansion in a new enterprise, growth resulting from the development of reproduction, is expanded reproduction on the scale of the enterprise. In this case, the entrepreneur must act quickly and wisely. More precisely, he must be ready to solve emerging issues and problems promptly, that is, immediately.

Conclusions and suggestions: managers play an important role in the economic life of a newly formed enterprise, we should not forget that in some cases it is better for experienced managers to open, form and create a new one than to reorganize an old one; based on experience, it should be said that managers rely on the place and role of marketing in the long-term success of the enterprise. Marketing is a business lever for capturing the market, so without marketing, activity is zero; after the launch of a new enterprise, its future depends on its rational management, in which, in the management of the enterprise's activities, marketing and management must be coordinated with each other, and this is a serious issue. Here we are talking about the prospects of the enterprise. Therefore, this management is not just management, but strategic management with a long-term perspective; the sooner new entrepreneurs understand the secrets of economic growth, the more important it is. When it comes to economic growth, the best strategy is to increase domestic demand.

1. Thus, in conclusion, entrepreneurial activity in our country has its own special evolution, and it was concluded that entrepreneurship has been re-established and developed in our country during the years of independence. Concluding on the stages, it is clear from the study of the second stage that the accession of Central Asia to Russia was the impetus for the rapid development of market relations and entrepreneurship. However, this does not mean the general conclusion that the origin and "fate" of entrepreneurship in the Central Asian region depends entirely on Russian capital. However, the historical evolution of entrepreneurship (in the fetal or embryonic state) has its deep roots, a process that took place "before the merger".

2. From the above conclusion, it should be noted that the annexation of Central Asia to Russia has accelerated the process of entrepreneurship evolution, and it is so. In addition to the negative consequences of this "joining", there were also progressive aspects. It would be appropriate to cite one of the ideas found in the scientific literature on this subject. As V. Lavrentiev suggested: The occupation of Turkestan provided an unlimited number of opportunities for young Russian capital - especially the textile industry - to expand sales markets. Accordingly, Russian trade capital not only stimulated the economic basis of the "Asian mode of production", but also developed itself on this basis [13]. However, the downside of this "accession" affecting the economy of the former Turkestan is its colonial nature. Therefore: "Colonialism has served as a stimulus for the development of Russian entrepreneurship".

3. Definitely, entrepreneurship, the history of our country was re-formed during the "NEP" and was the main socio-economic force, the basis for the recovery of the country's economy. As a result, the economy of the young Soviet state recovered and fell in the direction of the government.

According to the environment created here, entrepreneurship took many forms and appearances. Due to its historical significance, the NEP period was a separate stage in the evolution of entrepreneurship in our study.

4. In the era of socialism, despite the fact that the term "entrepreneurship" is not used legally, entrepreneurship has acted in the economic life of the country in formal and informal forms. Officially, in particular, in the form of state-owned enterprises. Unofficially, it is located in the "hidden economy" in the form of various small industries, services, trade and financial markets. The historical significance of this stage is the achievements of the Soviet Union in foreign economic activity, which emerged in the international arena as a capital-producing entrepreneurial state and functioned significantly. At the same time, business concessions were mainly in the form of joint ventures, joint stock companies. In terms of activities, in particular, foreign trade played a key role, as well as insurance business. Of course, the lessons of entrepreneurship in this period are important for the development of a market economy in New Uzbekistan. It is important to study the obstacles, experience, achievements and other influencing factors, to take into account the implementation of reforms in our country today, especially the expansion of state-owned enterprises abroad.

5. The results of the study of the evolution of entrepreneurship in our country, the level of modern entrepreneurial activity in Uzbekistan, have their long-standing roots. Therefore, the current level of success in the mentality of the people of Uzbekistan, the sense of entrepreneurship, the diligence of our people - a testament to the fact that the market relations and sources of entrepreneurship at the evolutionary stages have passed from generation to generation. According to this, the historical trend of entrepreneurship has been identified - Uzbekistan has its own special entrepreneurial evolution. It was concluded that entrepreneurship has been re-established during the years of independence, settled in our country and is currently developing rapidly. This mentality of our people plays a key role in building a national "Uzbek model" of market economy in our country.

6. If we compare the stages of development of entrepreneurship, in the current situation, the most striking change is that in our country it is necessary to remember cotton growing, which has been a direct object in the direction of entrepreneurial activity. If the economy of Uzbekistan was a raw material base before independence, both in the era of capitalism and socialism, at a new stage the situation has changed radically. The Uzbek economy has gradually been freed from being a raw material base. The "Action Strategy" was adopted, a system of clusters was established in the country, and due to their complex activities (processing of raw materials in our country), a value chain mechanism was established, and in short, the transition to the production of finished products. Therefore, the export potential of our country is growing. So, it is safe to say that the new stage is a stage of increasing the number of entrepreneurs producing ready-made products for export.

7. In general, it can be concluded that entrepreneurship in our country has become a leading force in ensuring the intended development strategy of New Uzbekistan. Therefore, it is necessary to further increase the freedom of entrepreneurship in reforms aimed at improving the business environment, as well as to encourage competition. We also suggest that the business strategy should not ignore the invisible barriers to small and medium business development [12].

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